

ARCTIC PASSION

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Deliverable D2.4: Synthesis reports on the status of the Arctic Data System

Summary

The deliverable reports on recent activities and outcomes of the Arctic Data Committee (ADC), related working groups, and the Polar Data Forum. A consortium of polar data coordinating bodies (including the ADC, the Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management (SCADM), and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS)) has in the last decade hosted a number of workshops and events to foster collaboration between individuals, institutions, projects and organisations. The consortium has identified a need for continued, detailed technical collaboration to advance polar data management and has adopted the *FAIR* principles (data should be *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable*, see box 1) as a useful framework for the collaboration.

The deliverable provides an overview of existing activities and outcomes of the ADC, related working group and Antarctic partners. This report covers these topics (see also the Table of Contents, below):

- Chapter 1: Polar data policies
- Chapter 2: Mapping the Arctic (Polar) Data Ecosystem
- Chapter 3: Enhancing data discovery
- Chapter 4: Enhancing data interoperability: Semantics and Vocabularies
- Chapter 5: Specification of data management requirements for Essential Arctic Variables (EAV) / Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs)
- Chapter 6: Organising information about observing assets

These activities will continue, and this deliverable should be seen as the first in series of continuous reporting. The next report is planned for the end of 2023.

The polar data community has discussed the rationale for better alignment of polar data policies, investigate recent developments in data-driven polar research, and identify core elements of new, aligned polar data policies. The process resulted in a report recommending ten fundamental principles for polar data policies (Chapter 1). What is still outstanding is to formulate aligned data policies and to establish governance and commitments to these. Recommendations on this could be an outcome of Arctic PASSION.

The flow of information about the Arctic has been described as an Arctic ‘information ecosystem’. It has been proposed that an ecosystem model can be used to document, understand, and possibly predict the nature and functioning of the system for flow of information. In order to address the *Findability* in *FAIR*, the project *Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem* (MPDE) has been initiated as a joint initiative of the ADC, SCADM and SOOS. The goal of the MPDE project is to document the relationships between data centres in the Arctic (polar) data ‘ecosystem’ (Chapter 2). The project contributes to the ambition of Arctic PASSION Task 2.1 “to identify core technologies used in the Arctic Data System and the datasets already served”. Arctic PASSION D2.5 (*Updated mapping of the Arctic Data System*) will provide a more detailed report on the project.

There is a significant amount of data centre catalogues of interest to polar researchers. This fragmentation makes it difficult for potential data users to find the most relevant data to address a particular question. The goal of single-window search for data has been common across polar science and research communities. *Federated search* allows users to search multiple data repositories simultaneously, without concern about underlying technical challenges. The *Polar Federated Data Search Working Group* (POLDER) has been initiated as a joint initiative of the ADC, SCADM and SOOS, and has formulated recommendations to the polar community on utilising the principle *Science on Schema.org* (SOSO) in support for the discovery of polar data (Chapter 3).

The interdisciplinary variation in scientific terminology leads to differences in how raw data, as well as data products, are described. This is an issue when attempting to merge or integrate measured variables acquired by different means or different researchers who could use different terminologies for the same variable. Consistent “semantics” can help resolve terminological confusion by providing references to understand the meaning of concepts, words or phrases, and their relationships. An aspect of the *Interoperability* in *FAIR* is using controlled vocabularies, glossaries, and ontologies, and the joint *IARPC/ADC Semantics Working group* works to develop recommendations on this (Chapter 4).

The *Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems* (ROADS) will set a course towards systematically defining the needed observing and data systems for the Arctic. ROADS will identify requirements for observing and data systems along with implementation strategies that support data interoperability. Task 1.1.b in Arctic PASSION will organise expert panels to define and implementing a set of *Shared Arctic Variables* (SAVs) (Chapter 5).

Current efforts within the Arctic observing community to build out the Arctic observing system would want to be able to address questions like *What observing facilities and activities already exist? Where are the gaps?, and Is there overlap?* As described, the data world has found the *FAIR* principles as a useful framework for organising observational data, and there have been similar deliberations when it comes to organising information about *observing assets* (i.e. cruises, expeditions, infrastructures, networks, observatories, etc.). The *Polar Observation Assets Working Group* is a working group of the *Committee on Observations and Networks* (CON) of the *Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks* (SAON) and works (among other things) to create a registry of polar observing networks, and to formulate recommendations for adoption and implementation of established standards and solutions for this information (Chapter 6).

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Background

A consortium of polar data coordinating bodies (including ADC, SCADM and SOOS) has in the last decade hosted a number of workshops and events to foster collaboration between individuals, institutions, projects and organisations. These events have built on polar data coordination efforts including progress made during the fourth *International Polar Year* (IPY, 2007-2009), and the Polar Data Forum (PDF) series (See box 2).

The consortium has identified a need for continued, detailed technical collaboration in order to advance polar data management and has adopted the *FAIR principles* (see box 1) as a useful framework for the collaboration. Initial discussions have established that true interoperability (the 'I' in *FAIR*) of polar-relevant data is an important goal but one that is likely to take considerable resources and years to achieve. In contrast discovery as in findability (the 'F' in *FAIR*) is more achievable and could be achieved by establishing standards for the description of data and standards for making these descriptions available. This so-called *discovery metadata interoperability* has been considered likely to be achievable without the deployment of significant resources beyond those already available. For this pragmatic reason, efforts have focused on integrating *discovery metadata* through the *FAIR* principles, rather than the larger problem of making the underlying data truly *FAIR*. The primary benefit of *discovery metadata* aggregation for the broader community is that it enables users to discover and access more data, which in turn will hopefully improve the robustness of conclusions in resulting knowledge products.

Standardized and well formatted *discovery metadata* is also a prerequisite for *federated search*. *Federated search* is a way to retrieve information from a variety of sources through a single search application. A user makes a single query request which is distributed to the underlying sources in the federation. The federated search then aggregates the results that are received from the sources for presentation to the user. Federated search can be used to integrate disparate data sources (See also section 3.1).

The *FAIR* principles were presented by Wilkinson *et al* (2016) and have significantly influenced data sharing and data policy developments. The paper was motivated by a need to define 'good data management' in a sense that would facilitate discovery and use of data by assisting humans and machines in their discovery of, access to, integration, and analysis of scientific data.

The *FAIR* principles assert that data should be *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable*.

- Findability refers to the capacity to search for and discover datasets.
- Accessibility is a measure of the ease with which information can be directly obtained or accessed once discovered.
- Interoperability is the degree to which independent data can be combined and integrated with one another, which can be facilitated by using consistent standards and vocabularies.
- Reusability means that the data can be put to multiple uses beyond its original purpose.

Reference: Wilkinson, M. D, Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., B. Mons, B. 2016. The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data*, 3 (2016), Article 160018, 10.1038/sdata.2016.18

Box 1. The FAIR principles

Polar Data Forum I (2013), Tokyo, Japan
Polar Data Forum II (2015), Waterloo, Ontario, Canada
Polar Data Forum III (2019), Helsinki, Finland
Polar Data Forum IV (2021), Den Haag, The Netherlands*)
Polar Data Planning Summit (2016), Boulder, Colorado
Polar Data and Systems Architecture Workshop (2018), Geneva, Switzerland
*) <https://polar-data-forum.org/>

The Polar Data Forum (PDF) convenes polar data holders to discuss more efficient use of polar data, especially through the promotion of the *FAIR* principles.

Box 2: List of recent working events for the polar data community

This deliverable synthesizes work done on in recent years by the polar data community (see Box 2 for events and Box 3 for deliverables), led by the Arctic Data Committee (ADC), the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS), but with a specific focus on Arctic relevance.

Report of IPY Data Management Workshop (2006)
Report on SAON Data Management Workshop (2010)
Workshop on Arctic Data Coordination (2012)
Workshop on Cyberinfrastructure for Polar Sciences (2013)
Response by the Polar Data Community to the OGC Request for Information on Arctic Spatial Data (2016)
OGC Arctic Spatial Data Pilot Phase I Report (2016)
Summary Report of Polar Connections Interoperability Workshop and Assessment Process (2017)
Arctic Science Ministerial Deliverable Statement submitted to the Second Arctic Science Ministerial (2018)

Box 3. List of recent polar data community deliverables

1. Polar data policies

1.1 Background

At the Polar Data Forum III, a wide data community with interest in data management, gathered to discuss the rationale for better alignment of polar data policies, investigate recent developments in data-driven polar research, identify core elements of new, aligned polar data policies, and identify organisations, projects, and people which should be the target of policies. The discussions at the Forum formed the starting point for the development of principles to align polar data policies throughout 2020-2021. The process, involving data managers and experts from international polar data committees in both the northern and southern hemispheres, resulted in a report recommending ten fundamental principles for polar data policies (Tronstad *et al*, 2021).

The work focused on core principles that could be relevant for communities supported by Arctic Data Committee (ADC)¹, the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS), so that the relevant communities can follow a common set of recommendations. The work examined the state and recent developments of global and important regional data policies, as well as technological and institutional developments that should or might be considered when forming new polar data policies.

1.2 Introduction

Through the transformative effects of digital technologies, data have become increasingly important resources not only for scientific research, but for economic development, environmental protection, resource management and human welfare. Data policies are important tools to set expectations among the science community and other rights holders and stakeholders about how and what data to share and how to treat data shared by others. As a primary resource for science and scientific collaboration, data should be managed according to widely recognised principles. A common data policy clarifies obligations and stipulate norms with respect to data sharing, access, management, preservation, and acknowledgment. Agreement on such principles facilitates collaborative research. For science coordinating bodies, funding agencies, research institutions, and scientists themselves, good data sharing policies and practices optimise the societal benefits and the scientific utility of data.

The fourth *International Polar Year* (IPY, 2007-2009) provided a major impetus to improving management of data from both poles and introduced a data policy specific to polar research. Following the IPY, individual data policies were developed by the polar science groups. In 2010, SCAR adopted a SCAR data policy prepared by its Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management (SCADM) and largely built on the IPY Data Policy. The International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) followed with its *Statement of Principles and Practices for Arctic Data Management*¹ in 2013, and established its Arctic Data Committee (ADC) together with SAON the following year. Finally, the SOOS Data Management Sub-Committee (DMSC) established a similar data policy in 2015. While the three polar data committees (SCADM, SOOS DMSC, and ADC) have developed data policies that are similar and while they share major ideas and obligations, the policies were not written to be explicitly aligned and differ in important aspects. In addition, they pre-date the widespread (*FAIR*) and emergent (*CARE*, *TRUST*) adoption of three key sets of principles for data management:

- FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Principles (Wilkinson *et al* 2016) that encourage machine-interoperability of datasets,

¹ The ADC does not formally have a data policy, but has made reference to the 'IASC Data Statement' (<https://iasc.info/our-work/data-and-observations/707-iasc-data-statement>)

- TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User Community, and Sustainability and Technology) Principles for trust-worthy data repositories (Lin *et al* 2020)
- CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) Principles for management of data about and collected by Indigenous people (Carroll *et al*, 2020).

1.3 Alignment of Polar Data Policies

As the institutional framework for international scientific collaboration evolves, so do the data policies of the global organisations, and these have been leading the way towards more sustainable management of the knowledge assets represented by scientific data. Through the *Polar to Global Online Interoperability and Data Sharing Workshops/Hackathons*² (P2G) work was organised to align polar data policies. The work involved the identification of the core principles, fundamental recommendations, and best practices emerging from overarching, global and regional data policies that polar data policies should be aligned with or consider. The work involved reviewing the policies

<p>Antarctic Treaty</p> <p>Antarctic Treaty Resolution</p> <p>World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Unified Policy for the International Exchange of Earth System Data</p> <p>Scientific Data and Information Report of the CSPR Assessment Panel</p> <p>International Polar Year 2007-2008 Data Policy</p> <p>OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding</p> <p>Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research Data Policy</p> <p>Statement of Principles and Practices for Arctic Data Management</p> <p>Southern Ocean Observing System Data Policy</p> <p>Open Data in a Big Data World: An International Accord</p> <p>World Data System Data Sharing Principles</p> <p>Global Earth Observation System of Systems Data Sharing Principles</p> <p>The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship</p> <p>Agreement on Enhancing International Arctic Scientific Cooperation</p> <p>CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance</p> <p>Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission Oceanographic Data Exchange Policy: Status Report</p> <p>American Geophysical Union Position Statement on Data</p> <p>The Beijing Declaration on Research Data</p> <p>European Union Open Data Directive</p> <p>European Strategy for data</p> <p>Proposal for a Regulation on European data governance (Data Governance Act)</p>
<p>Box 1.1 <u>Tronstad <i>et al</i> (2021) was prepared with reference to the data policies listed in the table and attempted to be compatible with them all.</u></p>

² Since 2020, the ADC, SCAR and SOOS have organized the *Polar to Global Online Interoperability and Data Sharing Workshops/Hackathons*: <https://arcticdc.org/meetings/conference-calls-webinars/polar-to-global-online-interoperability-and-data-sharing-workshop-hackathon>

of these global initiatives: International Science Council (ISC), UNESCO, WMO, IOC, UN-GGIM, OECD, Group on Earth Observations (GEO). In addition, the policies of the following regional initiatives were reviewed: Antarctic Treaty, Agreement on Enhancing International Arctic Scientific Cooperation, the European Union Open Data Directive (2017) and the IPY Data Policy (See Box 1.1).

1.4 Key objectives

That publicly funded research data, including nearly all research data from the polar regions, should be regarded as a public asset, and managed in a way that will maximise their benefit to society has become an almost universal presumption of global scientific organisations, governments, and funding agencies. Like the IPY data policy, updated polar data policies should aim to “provide a framework for these data to be handled in a consistent manner, and to strike a balance between the rights of investigators, the rights of Indigenous peoples, and the need for widespread access through the free and unrestricted sharing and exchange of both data and metadata.”

Research data policies aim to promote scientific cooperation and scientific advancement, to improve the efficiency and quality of science, and to enhance the scientific productivity of data. The latter is of particular interest to polar research, where data collection tends to be particularly expensive, and duplication of data collection efforts are correspondingly undesirable. Even more importantly, the management of polar data and all other research data should serve to ensure transparency and reproducibility in science, and to preserve scientific legacies over the long-term.

Improving the scientific productivity of research data allows users to generate more knowledge per collected dataset, but it requires a more streamlined data flow. Good data policies can promote this by stipulating best practice requirements wherever it can be observed that current practices are impeding the free and open exchange of research data. By the same measures the hope is to highlight gaps in knowledge, induce innovation and the proliferation of ideas, and stimulate the search for new knowledge.

1.5 Recommended core principles for polar data policies

Scientific advancement depends on cooperation among researchers, policy makers, government, rights holders, residents, and other members of the public, crossing scientific disciplines and national boundaries. International data policies should serve to facilitate such collaboration.

Members of the Arctic, Antarctic, and Southern Ocean science communities work in nations, institutions, and disciplines that have varied laws and research and data policies. Data centres, funding agencies, and research institutions are encouraged to develop more specific policies and procedures to implement the policy elements formulated by Tronstad *et al* (2021) in a manner that aligns appropriately with local policy and legal requirements.

Tronstad *et al* (2021) presents ten fundamental principles that are widely acknowledged in global and regional data policies, and these should form the core of polar data policies as well. The set of principles can provide a foundation for an aligned view of how polar data and information should be curated, managed, and delivered. Tronstad *et al* (2021) should be consulted for a more comprehensive description of the principles:

1. **Data must be ethically open:** Data from publicly funded research should be open by design and by default to release their full potential as a primary resource for knowledge discovery. Full, free, and open access for all users should be the norm unless there are valid reasons for restricted

access. It is generally recognised that sharing and use of some data must remain partially or completely limited for ethical, cultural, or legal reasons. Valid reasons for such limitations may relate to privacy where human subjects are involved, safety, security, environment protection, and other ethical considerations, including protection of the rights of Indigenous peoples.

2. Data should be free: The distribution and reuse of research data should be free of charge and delivered at no more than the cost of reproduction and delivery.
3. Data must be provided in a timely manner: All research data should be made available as soon as possible after their collection and, if possible, near real-time. Some latency may be required for data processing, quality control, organizing data products, and (in some cases) peer review.
4. FAIR Principles should be applied to the greatest extent practicable: Findability and online data accessibility should be regarded as universal requirements. The FAIR principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data. These principles depend on community-agreed formats, languages, and vocabularies for both data and metadata.
5. All data must be accompanied by a complete set of metadata: All data must be accompanied by a full set of metadata that appropriately documents and describes the data. Structured, standardised metadata are essential to the discovery, access, and effective reuse of data, allowing users to assess the quality of the data and any processing that has been applied to it.
6. Data should have persistent and globally unique identifiers: Dataset identification is key to long-term data preservation, identification, attribution, data citation, provenance tracking, linking research data with scientific results, and tracking of the distribution and impact of data collections. Persistent and globally unique identifiers (PIDs) should be used for all data and remain linked to the data through republication or data aggregation processes.
7. Data must be labelled as reusable: Open data access and legal interoperability require that the rights to reuse the data are made clear to the user. The rights and obligations of the data originator and the data user should be declared by attaching a rights waiver, a public domain statement, or an internationally recognised data licence to the dataset.
8. Data sources should be attributable and attributed: Data citation is an essential element of good research practice. To recognise the valuable contributions of data providers and to enhance repeatability and transparency of research results, data users must formally acknowledge data authors and sources.
9. Data must be appropriately preserved for the long term: Given that the long-term value of data may not be recognised until many years after collection, preservation of data to ensure a lasting legacy of research programmes and projects is essential.
10. Data management and long-term curation must be planned and resourced: Proper planning of data management and long-term curation is an integral part of any scientific endeavour. Projects should develop data management plans in advance of collecting data. These should outline how any data captured, modelled or acquired will be managed both during the life of the program and beyond.

1.6 Perspectives

Even if polar data policies are formulated in agreement with the mentioned principles, there are still definitions that deserve an additional refinement, like providing data in a ‘timely manner’.

While the work on aligning data policies in a comprehensive way documents the principles that should be part of polar data policies, the work to formulate and implement these policies is still to be accomplished. Most important in terms of implementation is the related commitment and

governance. For such policies to have effect, they should ideally be implemented as international, legally binding agreements. Such implementation will often require adaptation of existing national, regional or global data policies which also affects polar data, a process that is time consuming and sometimes difficult.

1.7 References

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2. Mapping the Arctic (Polar) Data Ecosystem

2.1 Introduction

The Arctic region, society, and research community is complex and operates at multiple scales. The flow of information about the Arctic has been described as an Arctic ‘information ecosystem’. It has been proposed that an ecosystem model can be used to document, understand, and possibly predict the nature and functioning of the system for flow of information (Pulsifer *et al*, 2020).

2.2 The Nunaliit Atlas Framework for Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem (MPDE):

The MPDE project is the result of a collaboration between the ADC, SOOS, SCADM, PolarView, Pan-Arctic Options Project, the *Polar Data Discovery Enhancement Research Working Group* (POLDER), Carleton University Geomatics and Cartographic Research Centre (GCRC), SAON, IASC and Arctic PASSION.

The goal of the MPDE project is to document and record the relationships between and among entities in the polar data ecosystem. This may include data centres, data catalogues, organizations related to data management, funders or other components of interest to the community (see Pulsifer *et al* 2020 for background). The project was established to help better understand how to enhance the ecosystem to be more effective and efficient. As part of Task 2.1 in Arctic PASSION (‘Mapping the Arctic Data System’), work is ongoing to identify and describe polar data entities. Each data collection entity point (e.g. data centres or aggregating catalogues) is described through elements like location, starting date, maintaining organization, and how it is related to other collection points.

Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem		POLDER					
POLDER: Organization List							
Filter By Harvesting Catalog		Filter By Harvested Catalog					
Rows: 289	Export CSV						
Harvesting Catalog	Harvesting Catalog Homepage	Harvested Catalog	Harvested Catalog Link	Harvesting Status	Harvesting Frequency	Harvesting Protocol	Metadata_Standards
Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS)	https://www.aaos.org/aoos-data-resources/	DataONE	https://www.dataone.org/	At Present			
Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS)	https://www.aaos.org/aoos-data-resources/	Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity (KNB) Data Repository	https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/#data	It's Complicated			
Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS)	https://www.aaos.org/aoos-data-resources/	NASA Global Change Master Directory / Common Metadata Repository (GCMD/CMR)	https://gcmd.nasa.gov/	In Past			
Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS)	https://www.aaos.org/aoos-data-resources/	National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI)	https://www.ncsl.noaa.gov/	At Present			

Box 2.1. Table view of the database underlying the MPDE project. Each row represents a data centre catalogue. Link: https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/index.html?module=module.harvest_link_list

The Nunaliit Atlas Framework is an open-source software framework for creating atlas websites developed by the GCRC. It is highly customizable and allows for the creation of maps and other interactive visual representations of the underlying data. Using a mapping tool would allow a visual analysis of the system in order to identify ‘strong’ and ‘weak’ data centres and ‘strong’ and ‘weak’ connections. The analogy of a ‘key species’ (i.e. key data centres) has been used by Pulsifer *et al* (2020) in the discussion of the project.

Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem
POLDER

POLDER: Organization Graph Filter Catalogs ▾

Box 2.2. Organization graph or “node” graph. Link:
https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/index.html?module=module.harvest_link_graph

2.3 Preliminary documents and visual representations from the MPDE project

The first version of the atlas is available at the GCRC web site³. Box 2.1 is a table view of the database underlying the database, and each row represents a data centre catalogue. Box 2.2 is an organization graph or “node” graph: The clickable graph shows the relations between data centre catalogues. Nodes can be moved around, and ‘sticky notes’ can be created to view and clarify the connections. Box 2.3 is the ‘Organization Map’: The points show the locations of data centre catalogues.

2.4 Perspectives

As of December 2022, more than 81 aggregating data centres/catalogues have been listed by the MPDE project. A current effort is contacting individuals in charge of one or several of these catalogues and asking for their help in updating the current information and identifying experts in charge of other data centres catalogues.

The goal is to ensure that all records in the database underlying the atlas are associated with the right person in charge of maintaining that data centre/catalogue. In the long term, individual data managers should be able to directly maintain their respective information displayed in the Nunaliit Atlas.

³ <https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/index.html>

Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem

POLDER

POLDER: Organization Map

Box 2.3. 'Organization Map': The points show the locations of data centre catalogues. Link: https://mpde.gcrc.carleton.ca/index.html?module=module.catalog_location_map

2.5 References

Pulsifer, P.L., Kontar, Y., Berkman, P.A., Taylor, D.R.F. (2020). Information Ecology to Map the Arctic Information Ecosystem. In: Young, O., Berkman, P., Vylegzhanin, A. (eds) Governing Arctic Seas: Regional Lessons from the Bering Strait and Barents Sea. Informed Decisionmaking for Sustainability. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-25674-6_12

3. Enhancing data discovery: Reporting on the progress of the joint SOOS/SCADM/ADC Polar Federated Search Working Group (POLDER)

3.1 Background

Given the diversity of nations, institutions, and scientific communities that collect data in the polar regions, it is very hard for data consumers to find and access the data relevant for their activity. Currently (December 2022), there is a significant amount of data centres/catalogues of interest to polar researchers (see e.g. Chapter 2). This fragmentation makes it difficult for potential data users to find the most relevant data to address a particular question.

Federated search allows users to search multiple data repositories simultaneously, without concern about a series of underlying technical challenges, including questions about interoperability. While an ideal *federated search* tool will allow retrieval and aggregation of data across repositories, this is also a goal that will take time to achieve. In the meantime, current efforts are focused on establishing *federated search* for metadata. The principle is that a dataset is described in an overall, standardized way and that it is this description (*discovery metadata*) that is the target for *federated search*. Federated *discovery metadata* search is dependent on the data centres that host polar-relevant data being able to present discovery metadata in a standardized way. Currently this is rare which means that the user must be able to translate metadata records between different standards.

The *Polar Federated Data Search Working Group* (POLDER)⁴ is a working group of the ADC⁵, SCADM⁶, and SOOS⁷, tasked with exploring ways to make federated search achievable for a technologically fragmented international community. *Science on Schema.org* (SOSO) is an initiative that formulates recommendations on vocabularies for scientific datasets, and POLDER has developing guidance for the implementation of *schema.org* (SDO) (see section 3.2) as a *discovery metadata* standard.

3.2 Schema.org and Science on Schema.Org

Schema.org (SDO) is a community activity with a mission to create, maintain, and promote standardized models for different types of data (*schemas*). It works through embedding information elements that search engines can extract in web pages. A driver for implementing SDO is that it allows Google Dataset Search (GDSS) to retrieve structured information from web pages that are maintained by data repositories.

A data repository can maintain a web page for each of their data sets with a description of the data set, a so-called *metadata landing page*. Once a data repository has implemented SDO in their dataset landing pages, they can become discoverable in GDSS. Google, however, does not hold copies of the data itself. Instead, users who discover data in GDSS are referred back to the repository to get access to the data. This means that access restrictions and protocols for data sharing, are maintained at the repository.

The principles of SDO are very generic, and the scientific community has organized a collaborative process through the *Earth Science Information Partners* (ESIP) called *Science on Schema.Org* (SOSO) to provide guidance on implementation of *schema.org* for scientific datasets, data repositories, and

⁴ <https://polder.info/>

⁵ <https://arcticdc.org/>

⁶ <https://www.scar.org/resources/scadm/overview/>

⁷ <https://soos.aq/>

more.

3.3 Polar Federated Search: Best practice guide to implementing *schema.org* (SDO) for (polar) data discovery

There could be many reasons for a data repository to implement SDO principles on data landing pages. As described above, this could simply be to present data to a user through GDSS. In a more sophisticated situation, it could also be to support the development of very advanced domain specific data discovery, access and analysis tools.

POLDER has a goal to “support the development of a federated polar data discovery portal” and is developing further guidance on how to implement SDO in the polar data community. It is currently (December 2022) drafting the document *Best practice guide to implementing schema.org for data discovery*⁸. The document is an outline of the required and recommended SDO terms that data repositories would need to implement in their metadata landing pages. For effective searching of most natural and social science data, Indigenous knowledge, and other polar datasets, more information is needed than the basic requirements that GDSS demands. The elements considered mandatory for polar federated search are identified in Box 3.1. These are deemed necessary to support querying on temporal coverage, spatial coverage and parameters/variables. In addition, they should be supplied to properly credit the data sets discovered as well as to facilitate access to these.

- 1.1 Citation
 - 1.1.1 Creator
 - 1.1.2 Date published
 - 1.1.3 Identifier
- 1.2 Temporal coverage
 - 1.2.1 Dynamically updated datasets
 - 1.2.2 Discontinuous, cyclical or seasonal data
 - 1.2.3 Uncertain dates
 - 1.2.4 Deep time and chronometric dates
- 1.3 Spatial coverage
 - 1.3.1 Place names
- 1.4 Parameters/Variables Measured
- 1.5 Licensing
- 1.6 Pointing to full metadata records
- 1.7 contentUrl link

Box 3.1: POLDER required fields

3.4 Perspectives

Federated search for polar data has been realized through a series of facilities, including:

- In collaboration with the World Data System's International Technology Office⁹, POLDER has developed the *Federated Search Tool*¹⁰. It can search a (limited) number of polar data

⁸

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1r4OSRuVBfdJpMbyhjkghHSeckraFEhxs0f1ld4aGkg/edit#heading=h.7awder7hafgg>

⁹ <https://worlddatasystem.org/about/international-technology-office/>

repositories using text filters and temporal filters and is meant to serve an international community of polar researchers.

- *Arctic Data Federation*¹¹ is a prototype demonstration of the federated data discovery capabilities from DataONE. Currently the portal is configured to list only the Arctic datasets in DataONE but can be expanded to also list Antarctic data.
- The *SAON Data Portal*¹²: Data are hosted and served by contributing data centres which expose *discovery metadata* on their datasets. Once initiated, the portal will regularly harvest *discovery metadata* from the data centres, filter for polar data, and ingests these. The portal invites additional data centres to make their metadata available and be subject to harvesting.

Multiple information models and interoperability protocols are used by these services. A truly federated service will probably have to bridge between multiple technologies to serve the community, as the polar community has different frameworks they have to relate to due to external forcing mechanisms, like national and regional policies and frameworks as well as existing discipline specific data exchange frameworks.

3.5 References

Karen Payne, Chantelle Verhey: Schema.org for Research Data Managers: A Primer: <https://www.inderscience.com/info/ingeneral/forthcoming.php?jcode=ijbdm> (in press).

¹⁰ <https://search.polder.info/>

¹¹ <https://search.dataone.org/portals/polderdemo/About>

¹² <https://saon.met.no>

4. Enhancing data interoperability: Semantics and Vocabularies. Reporting on the progress of the joint IARPC/ADC Semantics Working group

4.1 Background

Scientific investigations, especially in the rapidly changing circumpolar regions, relies on cooperation among researchers, institutions, and nations/unions to share data and ideas, to achieve more robust understanding of conditions and processes. The terminology used to describe data and data products, is highly heterogeneous and is to a large extent neither following discipline or domain specific standards. The result is a strongly reduced interoperability which may cause misinterpretation of data and information as well as it is costly and resource consuming to integrate data and products across providers. This is especially true when attempting to merge or integrate measured variables acquired by different means or different researchers who could use different terminologies for the same variable. “Semantic approaches” can help resolve terminological confusion, by providing a set of consistent reference points to understand the meaning of concepts, words or phrases, and their relationships (See Box 4.1). Semantic approaches in this context includes application of a range of approaches from controlled vocabularies through ontologies offering relationships between concepts, enabling machine interpretation and enriching of data documentation. Scientists are concerned about proper description of processes and data. Data that does not adhere to basic semantic principles can be highly heterogeneous, and therefore very difficult to find and use.

While search engines like Google enable identification and access to resources of interest on the internet, the result of a ‘search’ often gives a myriad of ‘hits’, most of which may be irrelevant. Moreover, the outcome of a search can be incomplete, and there is typically no way of knowing if this is the case. As an example, one can currently search the internet for information about “CO2 flux” and “Carbon Dioxide flux”, and expect the results to be the same, as these two concepts are synonymous, or nearly so. Yet most typically there will be widely varying results, as these two concepts are not explicitly related by some simple assertion indicating “these are the same”.

There are also situations where the same word or set of words have different meanings, such as “litter” {“plant litter” OR “animals born together with a shared mother” OR “urban trash”}. More complex scenarios also exist. For example, the same word can have related, yet distinct meanings in different communities: in the geology community the term thermokarst refers to a kind of landform; however, to permafrost researchers, thermokarst refers to a process.

The *Interoperable* component of the *FAIR* principles has several aspects, and one of them is *semantics*. In brief, in the data world *semantics* are the rules and principles for organising data languages, a similar definition as it is for human languages. In both cases, it is crucial to speak the same language or to be able to translate precisely and consistently from one language to another.

Box 4.1: The concept of semantics

The need for semantics approaches is recognized at the highest level, and there is for instance an initiative to develop a ‘semantic layer’ for the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) -

4.2 Polar Semantics Working Group

Within the polar data community, the *Polar Semantics Working Group* has been established with the goal to formulate advice on developing relevant semantic principles for the management of polar data. The Working Group organises experts within semantics and vocabularies with experience relevant to the polar regions and has the ambition to engage data centres which are managing and publishing data as well as providing guidance to data providers. The Working Group was originally established as a joint effort between the ADC and the *Arctic Data Sub Team* of the *Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee* (IARPC).

The goal and activities of the Working Group include:

- Promote awareness of existing vocabularies and semantics initiatives to increase effectiveness and reduce or eliminate redundancy.
- Coordinate vocabularies and semantics development activities across the polar information community.
- Enable and organize regular communication within the community.
- Help members of the community connect to useful and interoperable vocabularies.
- Inform the polar community about broader activities), and act as ambassadors from the polar community to other initiatives.

Through these activities, the working group aims to enhance the uptake of effective, community-focused, and sustainably interoperable semantic technologies across polar communities.

4.2.1. Semantics - application

Semantic technologies are useful in many contexts in science and, in particular, for data management. They ensure a common understanding of the object studied (e.g. a glacier) as well as a common understanding of the features (parameters/variables) of the glacier that are observed and analysed. For *discovery metadata* (see above), semantics is needed for the correct interpretation of these. If for instance a URL is part of *discovery metadata*, then semantics will document to the user (human or machine) how to handle the URL.

Semantic experts are continuously developing tools and methodologies. However, without the combined effort of scientists with domain knowledge and semantic experts, data will be under-exploited. In the worst case, data will not be accessible for analysis, simply as their documentation is insufficient to ensure proper interpretation.

4.2.2. Vocabularies and Ontologies

Authors from the *Polar Semantics Working Group* are currently drafting a document with the title *Practical Advice to Data Centers to Make (Meta)Data more FAIR*. It formulates a series of recommendations on *metadata interoperability*, focused on interoperability of the descriptions of the data sets rather than interoperability of the data sets themselves. Some of the recommendations in the document are about semantics, including the recommendation to:

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6D2qJTkUuk>

- “Use existing publicly accessible, community consensus vocabularies and ontologies wherever they exist. If such resources are missing terms or relationships you need, work with the community to update the appropriate resources accordingly”.

There is a tendency for different data communities to develop their own vocabularies within their specific scope, but this is often a hindrance for efficient exchange of data as concepts in such often lack clear definitions as well as mappings to more general vocabularies. The Working Group will consequently promote awareness of existing vocabularies and semantics initiatives to increase effectiveness and reduce or eliminate redundancy. It has developed this overview of *Semantic Resource Types*:

- Controlled vocabulary: A list of terms controlled by some authority - e.g. a dropdown list.
- Glossary: A collection of terms and their definitions, possibly with synonyms - e.g. NSIDC's Cryosphere Glossary: <https://nsidc.org/cryosphere/glossary>
- Thesaurus: A structured controlled vocabulary where each term is annotated with information and/or metadata (e.g. definition, source) and its hierarchical, associative, or equivalence relationships to other terms in the thesaurus.
- Taxonomy: A hierarchy of terms organized as a tree structure without formal relationships to terms in other trees. Terms that are deeper in the tree (i.e. towards the leaves) may gain and lose properties relative to their ancestors.
- Ontology: A formal representation of knowledge, typically in a graph or network structure, with both human and machine-readable definitions, with logical relationships (axioms) between the terms, which together define a domain of knowledge.

The Working Group has organised a survey to identify relevant terminology resources for the polar community with a focus on the cryosphere and polar regions broadly¹⁴. Results will be reported in the document *Metadata Harvesting and the Polar Data Community*.

4.2.3. Other WG activities, including engagement in Polar Data Forum (PDF)

- Engagement in PDF III: The Working Group arranged a workshop to introduce the concepts and approaches of semantics. During the workshop, hands-on training and semantic development was addressed. Identification of relevant existing semantic resources, how to enhance these and use them was covered. See also Box 2 on PDF III.
- Engagement in PDF IV: The Working Group arranged a workshop focused on a gap analysis of vocabularies. There are numerous groups working on semantic harmonization, and overview of these was developed. It wanted to determine what the most common vocabularies are, how they are being used in polar settings, and to prioritize which would be useful to align next. The intention was also to ensure inclusion of Indigenous semantic resources and provide a platform for Indigenous projects to be included in polar semantic discussions. See also Box 2 on PDF IV.
- In preparation for the MOSAiC expedition¹⁵, members of the Working Group were engaged in linking MOSAiC parameter terminology to polar semantics resources. There has been a similar engagement with T-Mosaic¹⁶.
- Engagement in the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP). The initiative provides Science-on-Schema.org (SOSO) guidance (mentioned above).

¹⁴ The survey is found here: <https://tinyurl.com/PolarVocabs>. The outcome of the survey is found here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1623mpRjWQcIIDY_zWp_cBOCpFEaADhs4GwoJOMHS-gg/edit#gid=2003460971

¹⁵ <https://mosaic-expedition.org>

¹⁶ <https://www.t-mosaic.com/>

4.3 Perspectives

Activities of the IARPC/ADC Semantics Working group stalled for various reasons in 2022 but is in the process of being reactivated. The group is now evaluating past activities and categorising these into a prioritised list for the future work. The intention is to establish a list of clear deliverables aligned with the objectives of the group (listed above), in particular focusing on the knowledge and uptake of semantic resources among data centres and data providers.

5. Specification of data management requirements for Essential Arctic Variables (EAV) / Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs). Progress report.

5.1 Introduction

The intent of the *Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems* (ROADS) is to set a course towards systematically defining the needed observing and data systems for the Arctic and to specify how the various partners and players are going to collectively work towards achieving these systems. ROADS will identify requirements for observing and data systems along with implementation strategies that support data interoperability. Societal benefit objectives will be translated into requirements for the observing and data system and estimate the resources that will be needed to implement them.

5.2 Perspectives

The first SAVs are currently being developed by the US project RNA-CoObs (with focus on food sovereignty in Alaskan Indigenous coastal communities) and Arctic PASSION. Within Arctic PASSION it has been proposed to develop these SAV themes: Permafrost or *Living on frozen land* in the local community of Longyearbyen, Svalbard and the Canadian northern Indigenous community Tuktoyaktuk (linked to PS2 'Arctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service'); Wildfires in Finland's Saami region and the land of the Gwich'in in northwest America (linked to PS4 'Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA) Service'), and sea ice in Canadian waters on the northwest passage connected to safety issues for local inhabitants including Indigenous Communities and shipping (linked to PS6 'Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas' Service').

Each SAV under ROADS should fully specify the observing and data system requirements from acquisition through information dissemination. For each SAV identified, requirements for observing and a strategy for their implementation and timely data dissemination will be produced. These descriptions should be comprehensive of data collection, data management, analysis, system management, and dissemination. The requirements should be aligned with the Statement of Principles and Practices for Arctic Data Management¹, and the *FAIR* and *CARE* principles.

5.3 References

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6. Organising information about observing assets. Progress report from the Polar Observing Assets Working Group (POAwg)

6.1 Background

There are many facilities and portals that organise information about observing facilities and activities (*observing assets*¹⁷), but often they do not share the information, or do so in an inconsistent way with custom data structures, custom vocabularies, and typically with limited access. There are only a few standards for organising *observing assets* information.

The value of organising information about *observing assets* was documented in a study by Wohner *et al* (2021). The study builds on existing research site information and evaluates the value of adding a new observation site to a geographical region. In another study by Wohner *et al* (2020), they investigate the interoperability across six major sources that organise information about research sites (mainly with a terrestrial theme: DEIMS-SDR, ICOS, INTERACT, NEMSR, NEON, and SIOS). The work concludes that they only share five elements (Figure 6.1), and that only these few can be integrated without semantic challenges for harmonization and integration.

The solution is not just one master portal or a “one stop shop”, but many portals that have implemented standardised interoperability interfaces and information models. This principle would mean that information from existing portals can be stored and maintained appropriately by the source organisations, but also made available to harvesting procedures from other facilities. All can have their own internal procedures for organising the information and still be valid sources for *federated search*. The established solutions for the FAIRness and interoperability of *discovery metadata* describing datasets can be applied to data describing observing assets.

6.2 Polar Observing Assets Working Group (POAwg)

Current efforts within the Arctic observing community to build out the Arctic observing system would want to be able to address questions like *What observing assets already exist? Where are the gaps?, Is there overlap?, and How can we better plan, coordinate, and achieve objectives?* The *Polar Observation Assets Working Group* (POAwg)¹⁸ was established under the SAON *Committee on Observations and Networks* (CON) to improve the usability, discoverability, and interoperability of structured information about observing activities in the polar regions. POAwg has as goals to 1) make *observing assets* related information FAIR, and 2) promote best practices for interoperability. This will be achieved through the following three tasks:

6.2.1. Create a registry of polar observing networks, documenting asset-related metadata standards, semantic technologies, and transfer protocols in use

POAwg has been working on developing use cases for the registry and is currently finalising a data model for the registry. A first draft of the data model is available (figure 6.3). The group is also in the process of formulating requirements for the technical platform to host the registry.

¹⁷ The term *observing assets* has been proposed to cover facilities and activities like Cruises, Expeditions, Infrastructures, Networks, Observatories, Observing systems, Platforms, Research activities, Programs, Projects, Sensors, Sites, Stations, Transects. POAwg has proposed the formulation “*in situ* observing infrastructure such as individual sites or mobile platforms, as well as activities such as projects, campaigns, and initiatives”]

¹⁸ <https://www.polarobservingassets.org>

6.2.2. Build crosswalks and facilitate existing tools for translation across standards

Information about observing assets is named *assets metadata* in this context. POAwg works to define a set of core data fields (variables) that describe *observing assets*. An observing asset information data model can be established on the basis of so-called *crosswalks*. There are some fields that are applicable for all types of *observing assets*, and in a crosswalk, different existing data models are compared and fields that are identical or almost identical are identified. POAwg has worked to create crosswalks for *observing systems* and *observing sites*. This work documents that established systems often only share a few fields, but also that crosswalks are important for establishing joint standards (See figure 6.2) to assist with harmonization and aggregation.

6.2.3. Create recommendations for adoption and implementation of established standards and solutions

This task will result in a guide to help individual networks/sources to create, populate, expand and deploy catalogues of *assets metadata*. This will save time and effort in meeting the sources' goals of sharing information in a structured way. POAwg is creating an overview of existing standards and has compiled documentation covering *observatories* and *field stations*, *observing networks/systems*, *observing sites*, *observing transects* (ship tracks, buoy tracks, etc.) and *research projects*. The result will communicate an easier path for networks to populate, expand, and share metadata catalogues of *observing assets*, thereby improving overall interoperability while saving considerable time and effort.

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Figure 6.1: Investigating the interoperability across six major sources that organise information about research sites.

From Wohner *et al* (2020) (excerpt). The right-most columns (DEIMS-SDR, ICOS, INTERACT, NEMSR, NEON, and SIOS) represent six sources that organise information about *research sites*. The two left-most columns list elements (variables) used to hold information about *research sites*. The authors conclude that the sources only share five elements and that only these few can be integrated.

Existing fields across catalogues.								
Category	Field	DEIMS-SDR	ICOS	INTERACT	NEMSR	NEON	SIOS	Frequency
Affiliation	Participation in networks/Ris/projects	✓	only ICOS	only INTERACT	✓	only NEON	always SIOS	2
Data	Available data services	✓	×	×	×	×	×	1
Environmental Characteristics	Geology	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	2
Environmental Characteristics	Dominant Phenology Species/general vegetation description	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	2
Environmental Characteristics	Ecosystem Classification/Biome/NLCD	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	2
Environmental Characteristics	Climate	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	3
Environmental Characteristics	Mean annual temperature	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	3

Figure 6.2: A comparison of existing *observing assets* catalogues

The table compare existing observing assets catalogues and documents the need for standardisation. Courtesy Bill Manley (University of Colorado, USA)

Comparison across Site-Level Catalogs #1

AOV	ArcticLCC	SIOS	SnoTel	[GERI]
Project ID				Projects
Initiative	networks			Networks
Discipline				
Project Institution		Institution		Institution Name
Contact Name		Full Contact Name		Contact Name
Contact Email		e-mail		Contact Email
Contact Phone				
Contact Role				
Project Page				URL
Project Metadata Link				
Site Name	sitename	Observation Facility	Station Name	Site Name
Alternate ID1	sitecode	RIS ID(s)	Station Id	Site ID
Alternate ID2	siteid		Network Code	Short Name
Country	state			Country
Place	county		HUC Name, County Name, State Code	
Latitude (DD)	geolocation	TYPE (long, lat)	Latitude	Location
Longitude (DD)	geolocation	TYPE (long, lat)	Longitude	Location
Locational Accuracy				
Depth (m)				Elevation
Elevation (m)	geolocation	Height above sea level (m)	Elevation	Elevation
Site Start Year	begin_date	Start Date	Start Date	Operational Period
Site End Year	end_date	End Date	End Date	Operational Period
Collection Type		Type		Facility Type
GCMD Science and Services Keyword		Observed Variable		Observed Properties
GCMD Platform Keyword				
GCMD Instrument Keyword				
Data Page		Landing Page		
Data Page		Landing Page		URL
Site Abstract	comments	Site Information		General Description
		Instrument Model and Serial Number		Infrastructure

Not all fields map across without problems.

Figure 6.3. Draft data model for Registry of Polar Observing Systems

Metadata Model for the Registry of Polar Observing Systems ☆ 📄 🔄

Fil Rediger Se Indsæt Formatér Data Værktøjer Udvidelser Hjælp Sidste redigering blev foretaget for 6 dage siden af William Manley

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A1 fx Metadata Model for the Registry of Polar Observing Systems

	A	B	O	P	Q	R
1	Metadata Model for the Registry of Polar Observing Systems					
2	<i>potential database fields (aka metadata elements) to describe polar networks, focusing on interoperability parameters</i>					
3	<i>include also organizations with observing-related, asset-level metadata catalogs</i>					
4	Field Alias	AVG	Field Definition	Format	Example Entry	Comments
5	Network Information					
6	Network Name	5.0	Full name of the observing network	Text	Svalbard Integrated Arctic	should be unique; i.e., only one record for each unique netw
7	Network Abbreviation	4.9	Acronym or short name of the observing network	Text	SIOS	
8	Network Description	4.8	Short summary of the observing network, including geo	Text	An international observing	required?
9	Network Website	5.0	Link to the website for the observing network	URL	sios-svalbard.org	
10	Asset Types	4.7	Categorization of discrete infrastructure or coordinated	Controlled Vocabular	sites	required?
11	Link for Network Logo (or logo itself)	3.3	Link to an image showing the logo of the observing netw	URL	https://sios-svalbard.org/	required? link or logo image itself depends on front end as populate the registry database
12	Network RoPON ID	5.0	A unique alphanumeric identifier automatically generate	Text		After some discussion, consensus seemed to be to use a a PID, rather than a GUID/UUID How to generate? Sh DOH-like (DEIMS-like, ROR-like) URL to the network's landi
13	Operating Status	3.3				problematic field for networks; drop it? (relevant for sites, p other asset types).
14	Organization	3.9	The entity responsible for funding or operation of the ob	Text		There has been, and likely will be more, discussion about v operational organization from funding agency (and/or institu etc.); perhaps best to lump together for the purposes of this networks??
15	Organizational Country	3.6	Name of the country of the organization(s) responsible	Controlled Vocabular		
16	Organization Website	3.5	Link(s) to the website for the organization(s) responsibl	URL		
17	Comments	1.4				

Appendix 1. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
ADC	Arctic Data Committee
ASDI	Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics Principles for management of data about and collected by Indigenous people (Carroll <i>et al</i> , 2020)
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
GCRC	Carleton University Geomatics and Cartographic Research Centre
GDSS	Google Dataset Search
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
IARPC	Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee
IASC	International Arctic Science Committee
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic
IPY	International Polar Year
MPDE	Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem project
NEMSR	The National Environmental Monitoring Sites Register
NEON	National Ecological Observatory Network

Abbreviation	Meaning
PDF	Polar Data Forum
P2G	Polar to Global Online Interoperability and Data Sharing initiative
POAwg	Polar Observing Assets Working Group
POLDER	Polar Federated Search Working Group
RNA-CoObs	Research Networking Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic
ROADS	Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks
SAVs	Shared Arctic Variables
SAON CON	Committee on Observing and Networks. A committee under SAON
SCAR	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research
SCADM	Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management
SDO	Schema.org
SDGIO	UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) - Sustainable Development Goals Interface Ontology
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System
SOOS	Southern Ocean Observing System
SOSO	Science on Schema.org
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User Community, and Sustainability and Technology Principles for trust-worthy data repositories (Lin <i>et al</i> 2020)

Abbreviation	Meaning
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WMO	World Meteorological Organization